

Notes

Some Observations on Nickel(II) Complexes of Hydroxyaldimino Amino Acids

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During our studies on nickel(II) mixed chelates containing salicylideneamino acids and dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline)^{1,2} as we had occasion to use some nickel(II) salicylideneamino acid complexes as reported by Ray and Mukherjee³. The complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{salglyH})_2]^3$ [(salglyH)₂=salicylidene glycin] appears to date the only *bis* salicylideneamino acidato nickel(II) chelate. These authors have also reported an apparently four-coordinated monomeric $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})(\text{OH})_2]$ (sal $\alpha\text{-alanH}_2$ =salicylidene α -alanine) and a five-coordinated mixed chelate $[\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-alanH})(\text{sal}\text{-}\alpha\text{alan})]$ ($\alpha\text{-alanH}=\alpha\text{-alanine}$)³. Structures of these chelates had not been adequately supported by spectral and thermal data. In this note we have endeavoured to establish the identities and develop authentic synthetic procedures for some salicylidene amino acid chelates of nickel(II).

Experimental

Bis (salicylaldehydato) diaquo nickel(II)⁴ and *bis* (aminoacidato) diaquo nickel(II)⁵ were prepared by published procedures.

Bis (salicylideneglycinato) nickel(II) :

Method A : $[\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2(\text{sal})_2]$ (salH=salicylaldehyde ; 0.003 mol) and glycine (glyH ; 0.006 mol) were taken in 1 : 1 water-ethanol (20 ml) and refluxed for five minutes. The solution was filtered and the filtrate cooled in a refrigerator overnight. Violetish blue crystals were dried in air.

Method B : $[\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2(\text{gly})_2]$ (0.002 mol) and salicylaldehyde (0.004 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) were allowed to reflux for one hour. The precipitated compound was collected, triturated with water (10 ml) on a steam bath for five minutes, filtered and finally dried in air. The substance is insoluble in all common solvents.

Both the methods gave satisfactory analyses for $[\text{Ni}(\text{salglyH})_2]$ (Found : H₂O, 2.1 ; Ni, 13.7 ; N, 6.4 ; Calc : H₂O, 2.1 ; Ni, 13.9 ; N, 6.6 percent) 0.5H₂O.

Bis(salicylidene α -alaninato) nickel(II) :

Method A : $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal})_2]$ (0.002 mol) and α -alanine (0.004 mol) were taken in ethanol (40 ml)

and refluxed for ten minutes. The solution was filtered hot and the filtrate was allowed to stand for two hours. The blue needle shaped crystals were collected and dried in air. On allowing to stand overnight a mixture of blue and green crystals was obtained.

Method B : $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\alpha\text{-alan})_2$ (0.002 mol) and salicylaldehyde (0.004 mol) were refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) for fifteen minutes. After filtration the green solution was allowed to stand for two hours. Blue crystals were collected and dried in air. On standing for a longer period a mixture of blue and green crystals were obtained. The compound is insoluble in all common solvents.

Both the methods provided satisfactory analyses for $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alanH})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (Found : H₂O, 3.8 ; Ni, 12.4 ; N, 5.9 ; Calc : H₂O, 3.9 ; Ni, 12.5 ; N, 6.1 percent).

μ -Bis(salicylidene α -alaninato) Tetraaquodnickel(II) :

Method A : $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal})_2]$ (0.003 mole) and α -alanine (0.003 mol) in water (80 ml) were digested on a steam bath for one hour. A small amount of unreacted $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal})_2]$ was removed by filtration, the filtrate concentrated to 20 ml and left overnight in a refrigerator. The green crystals were collected, washed with cold water and ethanol and finally dried in air.

Method B : $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\alpha\text{-alan})_2]$ (0.003 mol) was dissolved in water (25 ml) and to this salicylaldehyde (0.003 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The solution was then cooled in ice for half an hour and the green crystals were collected and dried as in method A.

Both the methods gave good analytical results for $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})_2]$. Found : H₂O (thermo-gravimetric) 11.5 ; Ni, 20.2 ; N, 20.5 ; Calc : H₂O, 12.6 ; Ni, 20.5 ; N, 4.9 percent).

Results and Discussion

Bis(salicylideneglycinato) nickel(II) : This compound was originally prepared by Ray and Mukherjee by the reaction of aqueous glycine with an alcoholic suspension of *bis*(salicylaldehydato) diaquo nickel(II)³. We now find that this synthesis can be carried out in an entirely aqueous medium. We have also been able to produce the same substance by a template reaction between salicylaldehyde and *bis*(glycinato) diaquo nickel(II) in an entirely aqueous medium. Successful preparation of the complex in an entirely aqueous medium is certainly due to the thermodynamic stability⁶ of the complex, arising out of chelation, which resists any nucleophilic attack by H₂O on the azomethine carbon of the Schiff base. Both the preparations provide the expected magnetic moment (~ 3.0 B.M.). The solid state electronic spectrum reveals to absorption bands at 11.50 kK

and 17.50 kK. These are assigned to well known transitions⁷. ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ respectively in octahedral symmetry. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio 1.52 falls within the range of pseudooctahedral nickel(II) chelates⁸. The $10 Dq$ (ν_1) value of 11.5 kK indicates a good ligand field about nickel(II). The third transition is not discernible.

Bis(salicylidene α -alaninato) nickel(II) and μ -bis(salicylidene α -alaninato) tetraaquo nickel(II): Ray and Mukherjee obtained their (alleged) green coloured $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})]$ (with an apparent C.N.4) by the reaction of $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal})_2]$ with an excess of α -alanine (1:2.3) in aqueous solution. Their mixed complex $[\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-alanH})(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})]$ (with an apparent C.N.5) was obtained by the interaction of the same two reactants in alcoholic solution using a ratio 1:3.5.

Besides reproducing Ray and Mukherjee's method we have also obtained their green coloured product by (i) the reaction of *bis*(α -alaninato) diaquo nickel(II) with salicylaldehyde in the ratio 1:1 and (ii) the reaction of *bis*(salicylaldehydato) nickel(II) with α -alanine in aqueous medium again in the ratio 1:1. Our analyses point to the empirical formula $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})]$ rather than to $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})]$. Our product compares well with the compound reported by Theriot⁹ via reaction of aqueous nickel(II) acetate with aqueous alcoholic solution of α -alanine and salicylaldehyde. The magnetic moments of these preparations are in the expected range (3.13-3.15 B.M.) for pseudooctahedral nickel(II). The ν_1 and ν_2 bands in the mull spectrum appear at 10.60 kK and 15.6 kK. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio of 1.42 is also indicative of a pseudooctahedral structure. The ν_1 and ν_2 bands (11.24 kK and 16.45 kK) as reported by Theriot⁹ seem to be erroneous as the ν_1 band indicates too high a $10 Dq$ for a complex with an $[\text{NiNO}_6]$ chromophore. Thus for the green complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})]$ of Ray and Mukherjee we suggest a μ -*bis*(salicylidene α -alaninato) tetraaquo nickel(II): $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})_2]$ with the H_2O molecules occupying *trans* apical sites of the two pseudooctahedral nickel(II) [c.f. the structures of nickel(II)⁹, cobalt(II)¹⁰ and manganese(II)¹¹ chelates of similar hydroxy aldiminoamino acids]. A thermogravimetric study shows loss of two H_2O molecules per nickel over the temperature range 50-200°.

We have not been able to reproduce the synthesis of the alleged five-coordinate $[\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-alanH})(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})]$, all variations of which led to the blue coloured $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alanH})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The mixed chelate formulation (with a C.N. 5 would require a sharp NH stretch (due to $\alpha\text{-alanH}$) and a rich electronic spectrum (with a characteristic band around 7 kK)¹². The infrared spectrum of the monohydrate $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alanH})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ records only a weak broad absorption around 3400 cm^{-1} which is evidently due to the lattice water that it carries. The solid state spectrum to the complex reveals only two bands: ν_1 at

11.49 kK and ν_2 at 18.01 kK but none at lower energy. Again ν_2/ν_1 ratio 1.57 is indicative of a pseudooctahedral stereochemistry.

Scheme I: Formation and reactions of salicylidene α -alanine complex of nickel (II).

It is interest to note that digestion of $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alanH})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with hot water slowly converts it to the green coloured $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{sal } \alpha\text{-alan})]$, indicating partial nucleophilic attack on one of the two C=N bonds. Scheme I gives the formation and some reactions of salicylidene α -alanine complexes of nickel(II).

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